

Towards implementation of segmentation into Physical geomorphometry tools: Case of generalization

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Abstract— The Physical Geomorphometry Tools project aims to develop a segmentation tool for physically based land surface segmentation, integrating with the new generalization and land surface parameters (LSP) calculator tools. This study evaluates the segmentation process across a complex, geomorphologically diverse area in western Slovakia, characterized by various landforms. The generalization of the digital elevation model (DEM) was conducted using a Quadric Error Metric (QEM) based method, preserving essential land surface features even at high generalization levels, and the K_0 index, the measure of kurtosis of curvature changes, was employed to determine optimal generalization levels, followed by segmentation using multiresolution segmentation (MRS). The study also assessed the Local Variance (LV) of geomorphometric variables within segments across different generalization levels. Results indicate that resampling the DEM at peak K_0 values enhances segmentation accuracy while maintaining an appropriate balance between terrain simplification and detail retention.

I. INTRODUCTION

Physical geomorphometry tools is a set of programs created within the project "Physical Geomorphometry for Physical Geographical Research" available on the website <https://xiceph.github.io/physical-geomorphometry-tools/>. We are working on the creation of a "segmentation" tool, which should provide elementary physically-based land surface segmentation in conjunction with the use of the other two tools "generalization" and "lsp-calculator".

Algorithm and applications of the elementary segmentation has recently been presented in [1] and [2]. The original algorithm [1] is more complex, its application in [2] is simplified. In both cases, very small areas were segmented, in the case of [2] also

genetically and morphostructurally homogeneous. Creating a universal segmentation tool requires a thorough examination of all segmentation steps over a much larger and more heterogeneous area, in connection with the main purpose of segmentation - digital geomorphological mapping.

The chosen area is situated in western Slovakia, within the Záhorie region, near the village of Plavecký Mikuláš at the junction of the Carpathians and the Vienna Basin with an extremely varied and enigmatic genesis (Fig.1). In its center there is a half-graben structure probably filled at the end of the Pleistocene with a paleolake, partially enclosed by a dune. The lake was probably catastrophically drained during a strong earthquake in the direction of today's flow of the Rudava River, which formed the unique features of its valley and very specific landslides occurred on the shore of the former lake, which were previously considered dune fields. This created an enigmatic set of aeolian, lacustrine, fluvial, tectonic and gravitational forms, which should be distinguished and aptly characterized by a good segmentation tool. The base DEM of the area was derived from Slovakia's Airborne Laser Scanning (ALS) data, provided by the Geodesy, Cartography, and Cadastre Authority of the Slovak Republic with resolution 1×1 m and vertical accuracy less than 7 cm.

Although the key role of generalization was emphasized in [1] and [2], only a simple smoothing of the surface by approximation by a polynomial in an increasing computational window was used. Therefore, as a first step in building our tool, we tested the use of our much more sophisticated "generalization" tool [3].

Figure 1. Selected study area (94 m²) with a hypsographic levels

II. EXPERIMENT DESIGN

A. Research questions

We were looking for answers to the following questions:

1. Can the new generalization method simplify the DEM so that the elementary forms of the different hierarchical levels are gradually emphasized in it?
2. Can the maximum of the K_0 index, recommended in [2], be used to select appropriate generalization levels?
3. How can the scale parameter be set for segmentation at a selected level of generalization? Can the Estimation of Scale Parameter (ESP) tool be used?
4. Does the simplified form of the algorithm [2] work well in even in more complex areas?

B. Generalization

The main task for land surface segmentation using high resolution DEMs involves creating a generalized model and computation of land surface parameters. The generalization of DEM was performed using method with QEM (Quadric Error Metric) approach, which even under high level of generalization is able to preserve significant land surface features [4]. The generalization process was repeated multiple times with varying numbers of iterations ranging from 0 to 1000, with a general increase in steps (e.g., increments of 5, 10, 50, 100, etc.). During this process, while keeping the resolution constant at 1×1 meter and the

sharpness parameter set to its default value (5), several new DEMs were generated.

To determine most suitable generalization level for segmentation, we used quantile-based measure of kurtosis (K_0) of concentration of data around zero. This measure was calculated from the third-order parameters (changes of plan and profile curvatures ($k_n)_{cc}$, ($k_n)_{cs}$, ($k_n)_{ss}$, and their average) across all generalized models at different levels of generalization [5].

$$K_0 = \frac{\tilde{x}_{95} - \tilde{x}_5}{\tilde{x}_{0+5} - \tilde{x}_{0-5}}$$

where \tilde{x}_{95} and \tilde{x}_5 are percentiles representing the spread of the set disregarding extreme values and \tilde{x}_{0+5} and \tilde{x}_{0-5} represent the fifth percentiles on the right and on the left from the zero value [6]. The generalization process was first applied to the original 1×1 m resolution DEM, where 300 iterations resulted in the most stable K_0 values. Based on this optimal level, the dataset was resampled to a 5×5 m resolution, followed by a second generalization process. The optimal K_0 at this stage was found at 115 iterations, after which a final resampling to 25×25 m was performed. The graphs (Fig. 2) indicate that generalization effectively enhances terrain representation up to a certain number of iterations, beyond which additional iterations no longer significantly improve segmentation. This suggests that an optimal K_0 should be determined before resampling to maintain an appropriate balance between terrain simplification and detail retention.

Figure 2. Values of K_0 derived from the third-order parameters and their average across different resolution. A – original 1×1 m resolution data, B – resampled 5×5 m resolution data, C – resampled 25×25 m resolution data

C. LSP calculation

After the generalization process, we calculated geomorphometric variables – derivatives using the LSP calculator with the *for_segmentation* flag and default polynomial degree of 3 [7]. These variables serve as inputs for the segmentation process. The calculated parameters include first-order: sine of slope, sine and cosine of aspect; second-order: normal slope line and contour curvature ($(k_n)_s$, $(k_n)_c$) and contour torsion (τ_c); third-order: contour change of normal contour curvature ($(k_n)_{cc}$), slope line change of normal contour curvature ($(k_n)_{cs}$) and slope line change of normal slope line curvature ($(k_n)_{ss}$). Curvatures and their changes were normalized [8] and all layers were clipped and rescaled to value range of 0 – 255.

D. Segmentation

Multiresolution segmentation (MRS) was performed at selected generalization levels based on the K_0 curve in the original 1-m resolution, specifically at levels 0 (non-generalized DEM), 5, 10, 40, 70, 100, 200, 300, 400, 500, and 1000. Segmentation was performed using the eCognition Developer 9 software. At the reference generalization level of 300, corresponding to the maximum K_0 value, we applied the ESP2 tool [9] to determine the optimal scale parameter (SP). Due to computational complexity, the analysis was applied only to a section from the central part of the study area containing the landslide, with steps of 5, 10, and 100 at three hierarchical levels. Instead of relying solely on the values recommended by the ESP2 tool, we selected the local minimum of the rate of change curve, signaling a decrease in local variance (LV) of image segments at scale parameter 440.

For the MRS applied to the entire study area, we assigned weights of 0.5 to the sine and cosine of aspect, and the weights of slope and $(k_n)_{cs}$ were doubled, following recommendations of [1] and [2]. The default values for the shape and compactness parameters (0.1 and 0.5, respectively) were retained. With a SP of 440, a total of 998 segments were generated at the generalization level 300. We aim to maintain a similar number of segments across other generalization levels to enable a comparison of local variance (LV) between the segmentations. In addition to calculating total LV, we separately computed the LV of the first-order variables (referred to as LV1), and the LV of the second- and third-order variables (referred to as LV23). Such distinction was made to assess the impact of normalizing the values of the curvatures and their changes on the resulting LV.

For the second sequence of generalizations with a 5×5 m resolution, we considered the generalization level 115 as the reference. At this level, the segmentation with the selected SP 400 and default weights for shape and compactness resulted in 50 image objects.

III. RESULTS

On a non-generalized DEM, many segment boundaries follow artificial lines, such as roads or pipelines (Fig.3A). Even a slight generalization allows for the creation of geomorphologically more meaningful segments. At higher levels of generalization, increasing the weight of the shape and compactness parameters (to 0.4 and 0.6, respectively) led to delineation of genetically homogeneous segments, such as the Sahara landslide (Fig.3C). The highly generalized DEM (Fig. 3D) is oversegmented using 53 segments. Segmentation with 7 segments, highlighting the main landforms, is more adequate.

Figure 3. Elevation on generalized data with segmentation on a hillshade: A – original data (1×1 m), 998 seg., B – 300 iterations (1×1 m), 998 seg., C – 115 iterations (5×5 m), 49 seg., D – 15 iterations (25×25 m), 53 seg., thicker lines 7 seg. The progression across the images illustrates the effect of the generalization process on the land surface, with increasing smoothness and simplification of terrain features.

Since normalization of second- and third-order LSPs emphasizes fluctuations of values around zero, the LV patterns for original and transformed curvature values differ. The LV curve calculated from the original curvature values (Fig.4) exhibits a sharp initial decline at the lowest generalization level (5), followed by a gradual decrease until it stabilizes around generalization level 200. This trend aligns with the behaviour of K_0 , which also flattens out around the same level (Fig. 2).

A different pattern is observed in the LV23 curve derived from normalized and rescaled curvature values (Fig.5), where two local maxima were detected at generalization levels 40 and 300, with corresponding local minima on the LV1 curve (Fig.5). We assume that at these generalization levels, the segmentation isolates objects that are homogeneous in terms of elevation, slope, and aspect, while allowing for slight fluctuations in curvatures and their changes. Since these generalization levels are also reflected

in the K_0 curve (with a sudden change in K_0 at level 40 and a maximum of K_0 at level 300 – Fig. 2), we consider the K_0 curve a suitable indicator to identify the optimal level of generalization when creating homogeneous segments.

Figure 4. Mean local variance (LV) of image objects on different generalization levels, calculated from original 2nd and 3rd order LSPs in 1-m resolution.

Figure 5. Mean local variance (LV) of image objects on different generalization levels, calculated from normalized and scaled LSPs in 1-m resolution.

IV. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The QEM-based generalization algorithm demonstrates strong performance, however as the number of iterations increases without adjusting the resolution, the effectiveness of generalization diminishes beyond the optimal K_0 . A key challenge is identifying the appropriate timing for resampling. Initial results indicate that resampling at the peak K_0 value may be the most effective strategy.

The local variance of normalized curvatures and changes of curvatures values behaves differently compared to the LV of the original values, which directly express geomorphic energy. This discrepancy would be problematic if we were strictly following the equilibrium paradigm as applied in [10], where only equilibrium elementary forms are considered. However, within a shift towards a non-equilibrium paradigm [1], this property becomes advantageous. By emphasizing low curvature values and changes in curvature while reducing the weight of high values, the method enhances the acceptance of highly non-equilibrium segments in the final segmentation results.

The ESP tool appears insufficient for identifying the most suitable SP, instead, it may be necessary to search for minima

beneath the trend line and the dependency of the local variance and average object size.

If the processed area contains highly contrasting morphostructures—such as a flat lake bottom, an aeolian hill, and a mountain foothill, as in our case—maximizing the K_0 index results in a generalization that is only suitable for segmenting the largest of these features. Therefore, generalization and subsequent segmentation should be conducted independently within the morphostructurally homogeneous areas, either based on expert-defined geomorphological units or regions identified through prior physically based morphostructural segmentation [11].

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